

REPORT

Inventory of good practices for developing multi-actor projects

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PREMIERE –
PREPARING MULTI-ACTOR PROJECTS
IN A CO-CREATIVE WAY

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ACRONYMS

Acronym	Long Form
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy of the EU
CAP Network	European Network of the Common Agricultural Policy
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution International Public License
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
D&E	Dissemination and Exploitation
DoA	Description of Actions
EC	European Commission
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
EIS	European Innovation Scoreboard
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation of the EU
Interreg	European Territorial Cooperation
ISS	Innovation Support Services
M6	Month 6
MA	Multi-Actor
MAA	Multi-Actor Approach
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
NCP	National Contact Point
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NRN	National Rural Network
OG	Operational Group (EIP-AGRI)
PA	Practice Abstract (in the common EIP-AGRI format)
PSG	Project Steering Group
REA	European Research Executive Agency
R&I	European Commission's Research and Innovation (R&I) framework
SCAR-AKIS SWG	Strategic Working Group of the Standing Committee on Agricultural Research for Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
SDG	United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
WP	Work Package

SUMMARY

The PREMIERE Inventory of good practices for developing multi-actor projects builds on a mix-method data gathering approach to present a structured inventory listing critical points, facilitating and hampering factors, and partnership practices leading to successful multi-actor approach (MAA) to proposal development. The inventory illustrates that often the success of a MA proposal is not dependent on completely novel factors but rather requires more nuanced understanding and engagement with factors that in general are relevant for developing a successful project proposal.

The report structures the success factors into five groups: (1) Predefined Factors – factors that, for the most part, the consortium needs to recognise and react to if consortium members aim to develop a project proposal; (2) Contextual Factors – diversity of capacities, experiences, professional profiles, and cultures partners bring to the consortia, as well as economic and social differences, differences in management and structure of organisations they represent, sectoral differences, etc.; (3) Motivation Factors – factors that capture aspects shaping the willingness/motivation of partners to be involved in the consortium and engage in the proposal development process; (4) Relational factors – those capturing the overall structure and different links between actors, which are individuals as well as partner organisations; (5) Skill-related factors – aspects related to experiences, knowledge, and skills that allow partners to develop a successful MA proposal.

The report lists the relevance of various factors as well as the prevalence of these factors across MA consortia. According to the quantitative survey, the five most relevant factors shaping the success of a MA proposal are (in the order of their relevance): Consortium partners' interest in the Call topic and project idea; Decisive leadership and advancement of the overall proposal development; Deep understanding of the objectives, scope, and expected impacts of the Call; Strong leadership skills of the coordinator; Clear identification and appropriate and balanced distribution of partner roles, tasks, and responsibilities.

The inventory lists the unique challenges faced by different stakeholder groups engaging with MA project proposals. It lists the challenges science, policy, industry and civic partners have when engaging in the MA consortia to develop a successful proposal.

1 INTRODUCTION

PREMIERE (Preparing multi-actor projects in a co-creative way) is an EU Horizon Europe (HE) project, which aims to strengthen the multi-actor approach (MAA) by supporting the development of more relevant, coherent, and well-prepared project proposals (see <https://premiere-multiactor.eu/>).

The present inventory is an output of the PREMIERE project, and more specifically of the work carried out in Task 3.1 “Rapid assessment of good practices in MA proposal preparation” as part of the broader effort of gathering and analysing insights, experiences, and good practices in the preparation of Horizon Europe multi-actor project proposals (WP3: Experiences, approaches and pathways) aimed at developing pathways for improved multi-actor (MA) project preparation in a co-creative way. The task was devoted to obtaining an inventory listing critical points, facilitating and hampering factors, and partnership practices based on several data sources. The results presented in this inventory also provide evidence-based input for different training materials and tools to be developed in the project.

The aim of this document is to serve as an inventory of good practices for developing MA project proposals. Based on multi-method data gathering it presents a structured collection of factors and accompanying principles thereof deemed important in the context of applying an MAA to proposal development. As such this inventory is intended to serve as a reference guide, offering not only the set of success (or potential failure) factors but also supporting these with practical examples in the form of quotes from the empirical material. This inventory thus provides a resource for sharing knowledge and experiences, helping teams or organisations learn from what has worked well or not so well in the past and apply these insights to future efforts.

It should be emphasised that many aspects that apply to MA project proposal development inevitably link into more generic aspects of managing transnational consortia and thus cannot be seen in isolation from those. For example, the data gathered illustrates the significance of having enough time as a crucial prerequisite of a successful MA proposal – a factor that undoubtedly is important for any proposal. MAA amplifies these factors and makes them more pronounced. In the context of MAA, the factor of time emerges as even more important as it is the prerequisite for ensuring an

inclusive discussion, developing trust between different groups of actors and ensuring partners' access to the well-functioning system of administrative support. Where possible the present analysis tries to highlight these specific takes on the different generic aspects either through illustrative quotes or more specific references to stakeholder groups (academia/ industry/ government/ civil society).

The present inventory is structured as follows. It first provides an overview of the methodology underlying the work carried out in conceptualising the process of MA proposal development and in obtaining and validating the empirical data for the analysis (Section 2). It then presents the findings by integrating insights from the different data sources, structured by five groups of factors that appeared relevant for the process of MA proposal preparation (Sections 3 through 7). The inventory then discusses the needs and challenges faced by specific actor groups (Section 8). Finally, it is rounded up by summarising the main conclusions stemming from the analysis and discussing some of the conceptual and methodological issues highlighted by this work that can help in further research into the multifaceted topic of MAA (Section 9).

The authors would like to take the opportunity to thank all project partners and the many participants outside the PREMIERE consortium who contributed with their views and experiences via the different engagement and data gathering formats employed in accomplishing this study.

2 METHODOLOGY

The results presented in the document are based on three sources of data:

- in-depth interviews,
- an online quantitative survey, and
- stakeholder workshops.

The methodological approach underlying the study assumes that at the starting stage of the study we have a substantial number of unknowns, and the task of the study is to capture these unknowns. Thus, the selected approach was designed to gradually move from an open approach to an ever more focused engagement with respondents. Because of that, we started to develop the inventory of good practices by interviewing actors who have been heavily engaged in developing MA project proposals. The diverse responses received were coded into statements that were then tested using a quantitative survey thus capturing the relevance of each tested factor in ensuring the success of an MA proposal allowing to develop the inventory of success factors.

Structurally, the following consecutive steps were taken:

- 1) First workshop: developing the first conceptual framework and validating it with project partners;
- 2) Semi-structured interviews: designing the interview guidelines in line with this framework and carrying out the semi-structured interviews;
- 3) Second workshop: verifying the results of the interviews in an interactive stakeholder session;
- 4) Online survey: designing, piloting and launching the online survey of different stakeholders having been engaged with MA proposal development, with a focus on enhancing the overall comprehension of factors that characterise work on successful MA project proposals;
- 5) Third workshop: discussing and validating the main conclusions with the project partners in a designated online workshop.

As such the methodological framework applied in the execution of this task employed a mixed-method approach (i.e. combining qualitative and quantitative research methods, as well as individual and group settings for data gathering) to allow for triangulation of results.

2.1 The first workshop

The first workshop was organised as part of the PREMIERE consortium meeting in Ebersvalde, Germany (27-29/02/2023), with the aim of co-creating

the conceptual framework underlying all the subsequent activities under this task. To prepare for the workshop, the initial analytical framework was developed based on the results of the LIASION project (<https://liaison2020.eu/>). More particularly, the initial framework focuses on three key dimensions of MA project development: project writing, partner search, and engaging with administrative issues. The objective of the workshop was to capture the diversity of experiences relevant to various actor groups to be discussed during the in-depth interviews and to provide a clear perspective on how to discuss and structure factors leading to the success of the MA proposal.

2.2 In-depth interviews

To obtain in-depth insights into the different aspects of MA proposal development process that would allow to both test and refine the initial assumptions regarding the key success factors to be tested in the stakeholder survey, qualitative research methodology was applied. This involved performing semi-structured interviews with a set of stakeholders along the three main blocks of questions dealing with the process of building the MA consortium, writing the MA proposal, and dealing with the administrative and technical management during the proposal development (see ANNEX 1). The guidelines for the interviews were based on the results of the 1st workshop.

In total, 12 online one-to-one interviews were carried out in June-July 2023 by four social scientists (BSC), incl. two female and two male researchers, with PREMIERE project partners and one non-project partner that were selected to represent different stakeholder groups, European regions, genders, and levels of experience with MA projects (see Table 1). Respondents were selected based on their experience in leading roles in MA project proposal development.

Table 1. Profile of the interviewees by gender, stakeholder group, and role in a proposal.

Gender		Stakeholder group				Role in the MAA proposal discussed	
Male	Female	Academia	Industry	Government	Civil society	Coordinator	Partner
4	8	7	2	0	3	4	8

While a balanced diversity was sought among the profiles of interviewees, it should be noted that there was a predominance of female informants, those speaking from the position of an MA project partner, and those representing academia. Yet, at the same time, it should be added that several of those

speaking as partners have also had experience while acting as project coordinators thus bringing in supplementary insights. Likewise, in terms of stakeholder groups, the predominance of research informants also needs to be interpreted with caution as even within the same category there was quite some variation with regard to the type of research institution the interviewees were affiliated to, e.g. based on the disciplinary profile, size, funding sources, and reach of the given organisation, not to mention the different sectoral backgrounds of the informants prior to their joining academia. Last, but not least, the classical quadruple helix classification along the four helices was at times challenging to apply, especially when thinking of consultancy service providers (hereby categorised under industry) or chambers of commerce that sit on the borderline of industry/government/civil society. To ensure that the obtained results capture *real* experiences rather than reflect common stereotypes, during the interviews respondents were asked to primarily focus on one MA proposal they have recently been engaged in.

All interviews took place on ZOOM or TEAMS platforms and were audio-recorded upon the consent of the informants. Each interview lasted between 30 and 90 minutes (most being around 50 minutes). The main points raised during the interview were then summarised in 3-4 pages of a pre-structured reporting template.

After all summaries were produced, all the different factors identified in the interviews along the three thematic blocks were compiled in a longlist to serve as an input for designing the stakeholder survey.

2.3 The second workshop

The second workshop was organised in person as a convened special session “Good practices in multi-actor collaboration for joint innovation projects” at the 26th European Seminar on Extension & Education (ESEE) in Toulouse, France (10-13/07/2023). This exercise, following the World Cafe methodology, aimed to verify the best practices obtained during the in-depth interviews for further use in designing the quantitative survey of stakeholders. During the workshop, the key success factors to be tested in the quantitative survey were identified. The workshop brought together 6 participants (see Table 2). The discussion took place as a special session of the congress and thus, the workshop was attended by those, who felt that the topic of the workshop reflects their interests.

Table 2. Profile of the workshop participants by gender and stakeholder group.

Gender		Stakeholder group			
Male	Female	Academia	Industry	Government	Civil society
3	3	5	1	0	0

2.4 Online survey

The online survey was designed with the aim of identifying the key factors leading to successful MA project proposals and key weaknesses limiting their successful development. The survey was structured to assess key elements influencing MA proposal development, including motivational, contextual, relational, skill-related, and predefined factors. It was tailored for individuals with experience in EU Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe MA projects, ensuring relevant and informed feedback. This criterion served for selecting survey participants, ensuring that the respondents have a direct understanding and experience of the complexities and challenges in MA project proposals.

The survey was carried out in November-December 2023 using the SurveyMonkey platform. This platform was chosen for its wide reach and accessibility, facilitating the participation of a diverse group of individuals. The survey ensured anonymity and ethical handling of data in line with best data protection practices.

The survey included a mix of Likert scale and open-ended questions, designed to provide both quantitative and qualitative insights into the factors affecting MA project proposal development. In total, 115 responses were received from participants across Europe (see Table 3). Responses were analysed using a combination of statistical and thematic analysis methods. This approach was used to extract both the empirical trends and the nuanced perspectives of the participants. The demographic questions were not set as obligatory and thus a substantial part of respondents chose not to answer these questions.

Table 3. Profile of the survey participants by gender and stakeholder group.

Gender			Stakeholder group					
Male	Female	No answer	Academia	Industry	Government	Civil society	Other	No answer
36	32	47	48	9	8	5	13	32

2.5 The third workshop

The last workshop was held online on 25 January 2024 through engagement of PREMIERE project partners with an aim of advancing a joint reflection about the results from the interviews and survey, which are crucial for the ongoing work in all WPs in the PREMIERE project. A total of 18 participants took part in the workshop (see Table 4).

Table 4. Profile of the workshop participants by gender and stakeholder group.

Gender		Stakeholder group			
Male	Female	Academia	Industry	Government	Civil society
5	13	14	4	0	0

2.6 Analytical clusters for the analysis of results

MA proposal preparation requires bringing together partners with different yet complementary expertise, skills, and knowledge. In the early phase of the PREMIERE project with the first workshop (see 2.1) followed by the preparation for the in-depth interviews (see 2.2), the inventory of factors leading to the development of successful MA project proposals were structured into five clusters, namely:

- Cluster ‘Predefined factors’,
- Cluster ‘Contextual factors’,
- Cluster ‘Motivational factors’,
- Cluster ‘Relational factors’,
- Cluster ‘Skill-related factors’.

The following Sections 3 to 7 present the results of the data collection of the mixed-method assessment including a detailed discussion of the factors identified. Section 8 discusses the needs of actor groups engaged in MA proposal writing. The concluding section focuses on two key aspects for further work in PREMIERE: the success of MA proposals (Section 9.1), and the writing of a successful MA proposal (Section 9.2). The report concludes with general reflections on the results of the Task 3.1 assessment (Section 9.3) and the methodology applied (Section 9.4).

3 PREDEFINED FACTORS

The cluster 'Predefined Factors' encompasses those aspects of developing an MA proposal that cannot be changed without strong justification or substantial effort. **These are the factors that, for the most part, the consortium needs to recognise and react to if consortium members aim to develop a project proposal.**

The so-called Predefined factors include the following aspects:

- Good understanding of the administrative, budgetary, reporting, and evaluation criteria of the Call;
- Purposeful selection of partners focusing on the partner profiles;
- Deep understanding of the objectives, scope, and expected impacts of the Call;
- The skills represented by the consortium mirroring the skillset in the Call;
- Time allocated for working out which are the right partners and the right focus for the proposal already in the early stages of proposal development;
- Internal formal consortium agreements are being developed and signed already at the stage of proposal development.

In every project proposal, there is a space for creativity. However, next to the creativity, there are also aspects that allow very little variation and tie the MA calls to very specific needs and tasks. These are aspects that emerge from the formulations used in the call – the issues proposals are expected to react to. The MA consortia must note these expectations and work with them accordingly, since not doing so will interfere with the possibility of the project being funded.

PREDEFINED FACTORS

Figure 1. Importance and frequency of implementation of predefined factors.

3.1 Good understanding of the administrative, budgetary, reporting, and evaluation criteria of the Call

While the vision of the project proposal is something that MA project partners are probably most interested in, it is not the only aspect that requires attention. To come up with a successful proposal, partners or at least the coordinator need to have a deep understanding of the technical side of the project Call. This includes various aspects. Some of these are more apparent such as the overall expected budget of the Call or the length of the project. However, there are also some less apparent MAA factors that need to be considered.

Firstly, the coordinator needs to have a **clear perspective on what exactly needs to be submitted** – what templates are available, what information needs to be provided, and how the information needs to be submitted. Secondly, the coordinator needs to **understand what information is expected from each invited partner**, who is eligible to participate, and whether there are any limitations that might be associated with particular types of MA partners. For example, a respondent explained that she would not recommend inviting partners from specific countries because the budgetary considerations

later might pose substantial challenges. Or, during a workshop, a participant recalled an experience where in an MA project aiming to be submitted as an Innovation Action it was discovered relatively late that partners making a profit would not be reimbursed costs in full.

Thirdly, the coordinator must **have a firm grasp of what exactly will be assessed** during the evaluation process, not least with regard to the coverage of MAA aspects. Several participants stated that the project evaluation form is among the first documents any coordinator should read.

3.2 Purposeful selection of partners focusing on the partner profiles listed in the Call

The profile of the consortium is an important prerequisite for success in any proposal. However, it is even more so in the case of MA proposals. In MA projects, partners must represent different stakeholder groups directly linked to the potential project results. To the project coordinator, this might pose two questions. Firstly, one must **identify who are the stakeholders that will benefit from the project**, and, secondly, **suited representatives of this group then need to be identified and invited to join**. The first challenge emerges from the fact that only some Calls explicitly suggest which MA partners should be invited to join the consortium. Meanwhile, most Calls remain somewhat ambiguous in this regard, giving emerging consortia some freedom. Yet, while there is this relative freedom, the chosen partners will have to capture both – the expectations of the Call and the vision of the proposal.

When the first challenge is resolved, a suited MA partner needs to be identified and invited to join the consortium. At this stage, decisions need to be made about the preferable profile and scope of the operations of the potential partner. During the in-depth interviews respondents recalled experiences when different proposals have decided to work either with large international/regional associations or joint forces with very small local groups of activists. Different approaches can thus be taken to set up a MA consortium. However, what united these stories was a deep understanding of how the choices made

“Ensuring a successful Multi Actor approach may be very difficult in some disciplines and/or sectors, as they are becoming more complex with many steps and stakeholders involved along the value chain, normally at international and local scale, and with strong interaction and links with other sectors. Thus, a proper identification of all actors’/stakeholders’ profiles is a key pre-requisite, sometimes not undertaken.”

were linked to the broader vision of what the consortium was aiming for. Thus, the selection of MA partners is a strategic choice that needs to be substantiated and linked to the strategic decisions consortia make.

Finally, when making this decision, one also needs to consider the motivation of the potential MA partner. The motivation can also be cultivated later during the project proposal development process. Moreover, the vision for the project will have to be adjusted once the full consortium is developed. However, it has to be kept in mind that in the long run it might be challenging to collaborate with somebody who does not share a general interest in the issues the MA project is planning to address.

3.3 Deep understanding of the objectives, scope, and expected impacts of the Call

The process of writing an MA proposal starts with identifying a relevant Call. There is no one right way how the initiators of the work on the proposal go about it. Some applicants monitor the potential Calls well before they are announced, while some Calls might be noticed by the potential consortium partners relatively late; some are identified by the project coordinator, while others are noticed by potential partners and are later passed to the potential coordinators, etc. However, once the Call is identified, it becomes a key reference point in proposal writing – it sets the key requirements the MA proposal should incorporate.

Firstly, the consortium must **have an understanding of the technical requirements of the Call**. This means acquainting oneself with the technical description of the Call and discussing the expectations set for the proposal. For example, Calls for different project types (‘Research and Innovation Action’, ‘Innovation Action’, and ‘Coordination and Support Action’) expect different results and consequently – different ways the project and the proposal are presented. These differences should be captured both in the description of the project proposal and in the structure of the MA consortium.

“My experience is in Community Supported Actions [CSAs], which require skills that are more transversal than in Innovation Actions [IAs] or Research and Innovation Actions [RIAs], meaning that in many cases many partners could “do the job”. What is more critical in selecting partners is: 1) partners that connect with the end-users, and 2) partners covering the geographical area of the CSA.”

Secondly, the consortium needs to **address the objectives listed in the Call** and formulate an MA perspective on how it will tie these objectives together. Often, Calls simultaneously raise objectives that might seem controversial and difficult to align. To formulate a perspective on how to engage with these objectives, representatives of the consortium need to unpack the general reasoning behind the Call. This involves close reading of the Call text, consultations with experts in the field, as well as engagement with published literature on the matter. However, if a matching MA consortium of experts is put together for the proposal, it should already incorporate this knowledge, and thus the rationale underlying the Call can be identified by having in-depth discussions within the consortium.

The results of the survey illustrate that this is among the most important factors for MA proposal development, and thus partners should spend time to get into the nuts and bolts of the particular Call topic text. The in-depth interviews also revealed that substantial problems come up when the consortium aims to submit an earlier proposal under a different Call (because they were not successful in the first application). Since the objectives highlighted in the subsequent Call are likely to be different to the earlier Call, the most difficult question the group need to answer refers to the level to which the proposal should be rewritten to align with the objectives, not least with regard to MAA focus.

3.4 The skills represented by the consortium mirror the skillset described in the Call

Project Calls can be very specific at times in what it is that is expected from the MA proposals. It is important to carefully read the Call and make sure that the consortium incorporates the competencies matching the expectations set by the Call. For instance, Research and Innovation Action

“It is not important that all partners have an ideal set of predefined factors, but that all competences needed for the proposal to succeed are included (e.g. at least one should understand the administrative aspects).”

projects will be focused on research and led by research organisations that are looking for non-academic partners to diversify their academic network. Meanwhile, a Thematic Network (which is a Coordination and Support Action) will be more practice-oriented with minimal research elements and not necessarily looking for researchers but promoting networking between the practitioners. Finally, Innovation Action projects will have to involve less research and more partners that ensure the implementation of existing

innovations. As in this type of project, SMEs are eligible only for 70% of funding, which introduces a different dynamic to the way partners might be selected to join the Call.

3.5 Time allocated to work out which are the right partners and the right focus for the proposal already in the early stages of proposal development

The selection of MA partners goes together with the development of the overall vision of the proposal. To align the structure of the consortium with the general idea behind the proposal, one needs to start to think about the way the two things will intertwine as soon as possible. For example, if the goal of the project is to develop an Advisory Network, it must be considered early on, which advisory organisations will be involved in the project and what other types of MA partners the consortium would benefit from.

“Time is implicit in many factors here. I think having time to develop the proposal and develop co-working processes, trust, bring partners up to speed on funding requirements, etc. Time is never provided!”

3.6 The internal formal consortium agreements are developed and signed already at the stage of proposal development

Some respondents during the qualitative interviews suggested that it is important for MA project consortia to **agree early on the issues related to intellectual property and public access to results**. Especially for enterprises, these factors might be relevant and might be a source of misunderstandings later in the project. The potential challenges might be addressed by signing legal agreements listing the main aspects of the collaboration already during the proposal development stage. This factor, however, was not acknowledged as very relevant by the respondents of the quantitative survey. From the factors assessed this was seen as the least relevant for a successful MA project proposal.

4 CONTEXTUAL FACTORS

It is not just the diverse knowledge that partners bring to the consortium. They also embody a **diversity of capacities, experiences, professional profiles, and cultures**. Partners also represent **economic and social differences, differences in management and structure of organisations** they represent, **sectoral differences**, etc. These diverse experiences form a unique background against which the project proposal needs to be co-developed. All these aspects can have an impact on how the consortium operates and, hence, these factors need to be accounted for.

The key Contextual factors identified are:

- Consortium partners have the administrative, financial, and staff capacity to work on the proposal;
- Consortium partners have previous general experience with the preparation and implementation of international projects;
- Within the consortium, there is an understanding of and willingness to adapt to the different national contexts that partners represent;
- Within the consortium, there is an understanding of and willingness to adapt to the diverse profiles and cultures of partners' organisations;
- The project coordinator understands and engages with regional/national and organisation-specific budget setting (incl. salary rates);
- The Consortium size is kept at the level that allows for maintaining an inclusive discussion, and a timely start of partner recruitment and proposal development.

Every activity happens in a particular context. While context is unavoidable, the impact it might have on the development of a successful MA proposal is ambiguous. One should also take into consideration the diversity of contexts that can affect the success of a proposal. The geographical context might manifest itself through different economic realities and cultures, sectoral and organisational contexts that produce different organisational cultures and capacities, and political contexts that manifest in different structural support arrangements. Accordingly, MA partners might come with all types of local elements attached to them. Results of the interviews, the survey, and the workshops illuminate slightly different results on this matter.

Respondents of the qualitative interviews present **context as a crucial element for developing a successful co-creation**. Workshop participants have also repeatedly raised concerns related to the context-related experiences of potential consortium partners. However, this sense of relevance is not shared at the same level by the respondents of the online survey. This is not, perhaps, very surprising. The context shaping MA partners' experiences in the consortium tends to be less visible than many other aspects. Thus, it might be difficult to capture its relevance with methods that do not allocate space for in-depth discussion.

Respondents of qualitative interviews provide illustrations of cases when context manifests itself. For example, achieving similar results might require different levels of engagement across Europe. This is because in one country the whole infrastructure needed to engage with the particular issue might be much more developed. Similarly, the level of readiness to engage in certain activities might differ in various countries, creating a situation where some partners might need to allocate significantly more effort to achieve the same results. Again – while the object the project engages with might be well defined and described in one country, in the other country the object might still be a novelty just starting to emerge. Another notable illustration is the time it takes to decide on different types of organisations or different sectors – in some (e.g. large pan-European organisations), the time needed might typically be longer due to backstopping and agreement along the agency's hierarchy.

In all the mentioned examples, a successful collaboration between MA partners presupposes sensitivity towards the different needs of consortium partners. Not recognising these differences will not always transform into roadblocks for the consortium, yet they certainly can hamper the process of proposal writing.

CONTEXTUAL FACTORS

Figure 2. Importance and frequency of implementation of contextual factors.

4.1 Consortium partners' administrative, financial, and staff capacity to work on the proposal

Organisations are facing a set of intellectual and administrative issues during the MA proposal writing process. This can be time-consuming. Organisations that are experienced with similar activities and have consciously made a decision to pursue the funding of international projects have developed official internal mechanisms that allow them to deal with these issues efficiently. For example, there might be templates, ready-made descriptions prepared to

“There are times when some partners are not suitable for Horizon project. They may not have the appropriate skills, organisational support, or provision to take on new staff to work on the project. People interested in Horizon, who have never worked on a research project previously, should improve their skills via smaller projects in LEADER or EIP-AGRI.”

simplify the work on funding bids, specialists with experience in various administrative issues, a designated share of paid working hours employees can allocate to work on the proposal, and even internal

grants aimed at supporting various needs that might emerge during the

proposal writing. On the other side of the spectrum, there might be organisations that have limited internal capacity and no support to engage with any kind of external activities. Most significantly, they might not have the paid working hours needed to advance the proposal and thus – every engagement for these organisations means an investment of staff's unpaid time.

Some respondents of interviews suggest that typically academic institutions are much better equipped to work on large-scale MA funding proposals because they have the tools and insights needed for such an effort. However, recently other large organisations (including professional organisations explicitly prioritising access to international grants) have been emerging as key actors being very well-equipped to pursue MA project funding. For a well-balanced MA proposal, project partners need to recognise the discrepancies in possibilities and internal resources possessed by different organisations and find a way to empower other actors who are invited to join the consortium.

One of the solutions raised by respondents of qualitative interviews is **for larger partner organisations to lend at least some of their capacity to the smaller, less prepared partners**. Practically, this might mean that larger and better-prepared partners share some of their ready-made forms and templates with all consortium partners. They often also devote some time to individually consult and support the new and smaller MA partners.

4.2 Consortium partners' previous experience with the preparation and implementation of international projects

This is one of the few factors that in the quantitative survey has received a higher evaluation for frequency of actual occurrence and a lower average rating for the assessed significance. This means the survey illustrates that partners' previous experience with proposals is more common among the partners of consortia than it possibly should be. Indeed, the qualitative interviews show that partners with international recognition are important, in particular when they have proven their ability to work on large-scale projects. The comparison of both types of data indicates that the significance of this aspect might sometimes be exaggerated and that consortium leaders could try to be **more open when it comes to identifying new MA partners and creating new channels for partners without earlier project experience**.

The common phenomenon of relying on **‘tested’ partners** is understandable. Proposal leaders are looking for MA partners with a clear understanding of administrative aspects of the submission process and have resolved all the issues that one might encounter (starting from simple things like ensuring that the organisation has a PIC number). Putting together a proposal can at times be a lonely task for the coordinator, and thus dedication from partners to provide support both intellectually and practically will be appreciated. Partners that have proven themselves to have this capacity can be an asset leading to successful proposal writing. Also, previous project experience of partners can help identify weak points in the proposal. Finally, if the proposal is successful, the project will have to be executed, and the initial choice of MA partners can make this process either very smooth or make it extremely challenging. Therefore, tested partners that have proven their value in the proposal writing and implementation phase will be engaged repeatedly.

With that being said, there are cases when the choice to engage a particular MA partner might not be fully justified. For example, workshops revealed that there are typical go-to partners that represent specific stakeholder groups in particular regions. Participants of the workshops explained that this approach might lead to having partners in the consortium who are poorly engaged and not very interested in the topic. Thus, the added value of these MA partners in practice will be limited. Yet the lack of knowledge about other partners and the limited time allocated to partner selection pushes the proposal coordinators to repeatedly return to the same group of well-known organisations.

4.3 Understanding of and willingness to adapt to different national contexts

National legislation and support institutions set limits to what various partners can do and what support they can count on when engaging in proposal writing. At least some **understanding of differences prevailing across the EU** might help the coordinator better understand the limitations different MA partners might encounter. For example, National Contact Points for Europe (NCPs) have different levels of experience across Europe. In some Member States, their recommendations are based on broad and long-term experience while other teams are new in this field of support. Additionally, having **an understanding of differences in work culture** across EU Member States represented in the consortium might help project coordinators foresee any potential pitfalls or sources of misunderstandings or even conflicts.

4.4 Understanding of and willingness to adapt to the diverse profiles and cultures of partner organisations

Organisational culture defines the ways organisations engage with the challenges they face. Some of them might be better prepared to adopt the "Horizon culture" and engage with MA project proposals while others might not be sufficiently equipped for that. Moreover, the coordinator most likely has a particular vision of how the work on the proposal will be carried out. This vision needs to be aligned with the different cultures and limitations of partner organisations. The organisational cultures of MA partners might not be able to accommodate all the expectations the coordinator has.

Furthermore, understanding the motivation of different stakeholder groups can help ensure that the proposal is capturing the interests of everybody because such insights feed e.g. into the stakeholder involvement and Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategies of the MA project proposal. One of the interviewed respondents explained that in the consortia she has been coordinating, there are partners who are not expected to provide written contributions. As the respondent explained – she knows that for that group of practice partners putting things on paper demands substantial effort. Yet, these partners are irreplaceable in providing their ideas in other forms (for example, in a co-creative workshop setting).

4.5 Understanding of and engagement with regional/national organisations including budget negotiations

This factor refers to e.g. salary rates and related negotiations. It sparked a lot of controversies among the participants of the workshops. Yet, it has not been embraced by the respondents of the quantitative survey. During the workshops, participants, especially those representing countries with comparatively lower average salaries, raised **concerns regarding unequal pay for a similar effort**. Participants have been stressing that budgets prepared for MA projects reflect deep inequalities that need to be addressed in the proposal writing process. The general argument explains that some of the countries are locked in lower salary rates, yet they have few instruments available to resolve the issue and escape the trap on their own. This leads to **unbalanced budgets** where partners from some countries receive substantially more funds for the same effort than others.

The notable differences in salary rates between MA partners might cause dissatisfaction among partners with the budget planning process and might be

a cause for a deeper feeling of inequality. Low salary rates might also lead to a situation where partners do not allocate the time needed to execute the work promised in the project or deliver poor-quality work. For this reason, transparency during the budget construction is a crucial element of the administrative MA proposal development process. Being transparent and providing convincing explanations from the coordinators' side might help to avoid situations where in particular smaller organisations are surprised (and disappointed) about the way the budget is being allocated among partner organisations.

There is no single clear solution on how to resolve the situation. However, in general, it is suggested that individual consultations with MA partners regarding the budget might help to address this issue and help create a deeper understanding within the consortium and highlight the challenges associated with budget planning. Still, this issue most likely is much deeper and cannot be fully resolved by a single project.

"We think that understanding the national context of partners is very important for building a good consortium. This includes transparent discussions about salary rates, etc. In our limited experience this was completely absent!"

4.6 Defining the size of the consortium by ensuring Member States' representation, budgetary and management constraints

"Ensuring a successful MA participation may require a high number of partners or collaborative engagement with many institutions, which may increase the number of partners in a consortium, thus reducing partners' funds or bringing serious coordination efforts."

The exchange of ideas is seen as key to ensuring the success of any proposal. During the interviews, respondents were keen to point out that often **the size of the consortium can be a barrier limiting successful internal discussions**. In other words, it might be difficult to maintain an inclusive MA debate in a large consortium.

This is because some partners might not be used to sharing their thoughts in large groups, more active/experienced partners might be very vocal/aggressive and impose their views, or simply - there might not be enough time to give voice to everybody. Yet **having everybody's voice heard** is a crucial precondition for the successful implementation of MAA.

This issue does not necessarily mean that small consortia will be more successful when it comes to MA project proposals. Instead, **coordinators need to consider how to ensure that all partners can engage**. It might mean scheduling extra meetings in sub-groups with partners responsible for particular tasks or developing other means of exchanging thoughts.

5 MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS

In MA project proposals, motivation is crucial and cannot be taken for granted. Not all partners will be equally motivated to participate and co-create. Furthermore, their motivation can change during the proposal development. The dynamics in partners' motivations are linked to their initial expectations, former personal and institutional experiences with similar proposals, as well as transparency related to setting project goals and objectives. **Motivational factors capture aspects that shape the willingness/motivation of partners to be involved in the consortium and engage in the proposal development process.**

The key Motivational factors to consider are:

- Consortium partners' interest in the Call topic and project idea;
- Consortium partners' feeling of ownership over the proposal development;
- Consortium partners' interest in the project's anticipated practical output;
- Consortium partners' commitment to devote time and effort to proposal writing;
- Consortium partners' willingness to collaborate with other types of multi-actor partners in the proposal development.

Partners' as well as coordinators' motivation is something they bring along when joining the MA consortium. However, motivation can also grow or vanish during the proposal writing process. One should also be sensitive regarding the object of motivation. On the one hand, motivation can be considered in the context of partners' general engagement with the Call topic and proposal writing. Some MA partners will be less engaged in discussing ideas to be advanced in the project and practically integrating those in the proposal text, while others will be more willing to allocate time for these activities. On the other hand, it could also be considered in the context of partners' willingness to engage in MAA. While some partners will be very motivated and open to engage at various stages of proposal development and explore the perspectives of various groups of stakeholders, others will appreciate the funding these projects deliver – yet they might not be enthusiastic about investing the time and effort needed to work on the transdisciplinary dialogue envisioned by the MAA.

The interviews with project participants illustrate that a lack of partners' motivation will not automatically disqualify MA proposals and render them invalid – there will always be differences between partners. There have been a lot of successful proposals with some poorly motivated partners participating in the project consortia. However, it is important that **the core team working on the proposal takes the partners' motivation seriously** and engages in overcoming the potential challenges linked to limited partner engagement. The way work in MAA will be organised can either encourage partners to engage more actively or discourage and potentially alienate them.

Figure 3. Importance and frequency of implementation of motivational factors.

5.1 Consortium partners' interest in the Call topic and project idea

According to the results of the quantitative survey, this is the most relevant factor determining the success of an MA project proposal. **Consortium partners need to be personally and professionally interested in the Call or the proposal to be willing to make the proposal successful.** However, the survey also illustrates that partners' interest in the topic might not always be there. To rephrase, respondents' expectations towards partners' interest in the topic are substantially higher than the assessed level of actual interest partners demonstrate. These findings have substantial implications for both MA consortium development and proposal writing.

Consortia can take shape in various ways. If, for example, the consortium is emerging from an already existing group of actors sharing common goals, ensuring a shared interest and a joint understanding of what these interests are might be easy. However, for consortia built from scratch, motivational factors are crucial to consider. One of the interviewed MA project leaders explained that one must take time to consider who might be interested in the topic. This should be done at every stage when the consortium is enlarged. It has also been suggested that **one must start thinking about potential future Calls early** – sometimes even years in advance. This allows for thoughtfully building and testing networks of MA partners even before the Call is announced.

5.2 Consortium partners' feeling of ownership over the proposal development

Ensuring that MA partners feel ownership over the proposal can help resolve several of the issues that are linked to proposal writing. A sense of ownership will help at all stages of proposal development, ensuring proactive engagement of partners, and can be crucial whenever a consortium faces unexpected challenges. Yet, when it comes to implementation, respondents of the survey suggest that this is one of the least common factors observed – in general, we can conclude that **for the most part partners do not feel very connected to the project proposals they are working with**. This most likely means that most of the responsibilities to push the MA proposal forward fall on the shoulders of the proposal leader and a smaller core group of people working on it.

One of the key reasons for partners not feeling such ownership, probably, is segmentation within the MA consortium. From the interviews, we observe that it is **common for consortia to be built in stages**, with some partners that are invited earlier to the project being much closer to the core team than others. Others are often invited to fill the gaps in terms of expertise or stakeholder groups identified in the proposal development process. This process automatically presupposes difficulties in ensuring that each MA partner has the same level of ownership and engagement with the proposal.

Interviews also illustrate that there are several ways how the sense of ownership can be strengthened – by organising bilateral meetings with partners, by pairing newer inexperienced MA partners with more seasoned partners, and by being transparent in setting project goals and objectives. The

project leader should also think about opportunities for partners to express their opinions and contribute to proposal development. All of these steps, however, also presuppose that the project leader has the capacity and the skills to engage in activities that could strengthen the feeling of proposal ownership.

5.3 Consortium partners' interest in the project's anticipated practical output

Projects are expected to deliver particular outputs. The outputs are among the elements of the MA proposal that are expected to bring different types of actors closer – these outputs should be developed to benefit from the diversity of experiences locked in the consortium. Interestingly, respondents of the survey present partners' interest in the practical outputs of the project as less relevant than partners' general interest in the topic of the project. However, this observation differs among various target groups. Two trends can be observed in the data. Firstly, the relevance of practical output drops as the age of the respondents increases. Secondly, the importance of the practical outputs drops with the increase in the number of projects respondents have been engaged in. However, it must also be noted that age and the number of projects one has been engaged in correlates.

"Multi-actor approaches often need to accommodate different vested interests or agendas. This is a challenge to ensure diversity while avoiding disruptive conflict (in case of controversial issues) or if only one grouping is included, then perceptions of bias one way or other."

With that being said, interviews illustrate that **the MA proposal must be clear regarding what it aims to achieve**. This clarity allows engaged stakeholders to be more efficient in developing the proposal text and the line of argumentation, as well as in selecting additional partners. It also allows the proposal to communicate to reviewers what exactly the consortium will

be doing and why this contribution is unique. The results of the workshops suggest that **engaging practice partners early and having regular consultations with all MA partners** can ensure that the planned practical outputs of the project are clear and meaningful.

5.4 Consortium partners' commitment to proposal writing

Writing a proposal is a tedious process. There is a handful of details that require attention and in-depth knowledge. It is a time-consuming endeavour. For proposals that adopt the MAA, this is even more pronounced. Partners engaged in such consortia represent different organisational contexts, work

cultures, and expectations that all need to be aligned. Time needs to be allocated by each partner organisation to participate in this collaborative work. On the one hand, this is an issue of availability of working hours for this task in partner organisations. Especially smaller organisations might discover that they do not have the necessary time to engage in extensive debates on the emerging proposal. On the other hand, this is an issue of the partners' willingness (priorities) to allocate time to the activity. Partners might be willing to have the possibility to compete for funding, yet they might be investing their time elsewhere. To develop a successful proposal and to make sure that the MAA principles are respected, invited partners need to be willing to engage. Meanwhile, to make the consortium well-balanced, proposal coordinators need to find a way to ensure continuous involvement of those partners that struggle to engage. During the interviews, the respondents stressed that, for MAA to work, the project leader needs to assess every partner individually and consider if there are any time-related or other restraints the particular partner might have and how these might be resolved.

The online survey included a quantitative assessment. This shows that motivational factors are among the top ten factors affecting the success of MA proposals. This factor is even more notable due to the perceived gap between its perceived importance and the assessed level of partners allocating sufficient time to work on the proposal. This factor is among the five lowest ranked factors when it comes to implementation. Moreover, the survey illustrates that **while partners are interested in joining a consortium, they are not always ready to fully commit to the actual proposal development.** This observation just reiterates the importance of the factor of partner selection.

5.5 Consortium partners' willingness to collaborate on an equal level

Partners' willingness to collaborate with partners that have another (e.g. non-academic) background or have other professional understanding and technical language is not perceived as a major factor affecting the success of the MA project proposals. Yet, it is perceived as one that is often missing in practice. According to the quantitative survey, there is a lot of space for improvement when it comes to partners' willingness to work together with other types of actors.

From the interviews, it is clear that not all partners need to be in a position where they have to collaborate and that not all partners will always enjoy

collaborative tasks shared with other types of actors engaged in the proposal. Yet, it is important to make sure that people who do not have the capacity or motivation to build bridges across different partner domains are not in project roles where it matters. Thus, the consortium needs to be aware of the need to collaborate and in which parts of the envisioned project it matters the most.

Interviews illustrate that some employment of simple means might facilitate co-creation. For

example, in some projects **pairing of partners** has worked well, in other projects – some partners have been engaged by using **individual consultations**, while some other respondents report that the right **online tools** can help harvest the joint knowledge without pushing all partners into deliberation. Thus, different solutions can be tailored to strengthen the MAA.

"I believe partners are all on a journey to understand truly and implement the multi-actor approach. Even those who value it in theory are still developing the tools to apply it in practice. Some partners really do not value the multi-actor process. I think a share fair conference on sharing best multi-actor practice for all organisations funded by the EU on multi-actor projects could go some way to inspiring change. Coaching and mentoring individuals in projects that are meant to be multi-actor but are not implemented in that way would also be useful. At the end of the day this is about developing everyone's people skills, particularly their facilitation skills. Perhaps it could be a requirement to attend a short course?"

6 RELATIONAL FACTORS

MA project proposals can be a space for power imbalances and can employ different work strategies manifesting such imbalances. Both of the aforementioned can harm the process of developing a successful MA project proposal. Thus, the process of proposal development needs management that helps overcome power imbalances in the consortium, ensures that the interests of engaged actors are heard, and, within reason, considers and creates interlinkages between different insights and practices partners bring to the table. Relational factors refer **to aspects that cover individual and organisational levels. It focuses on the overall structure and different links between actors, which are individuals as well as partner organisations.**

The key Relational factors to consider are:

- Timely start of partner recruitment and proposal development;
- Attraction of partners with prior positive personal collaboration experience;
- Clear identification and appropriate and balanced distribution of partner roles, tasks, and responsibilities;
- Decisive leadership and advancement of the overall proposal development;
- Transparent, participatory, and mutually respectful internal communication and decision-making;
- Skilful alignment of different personalities engaged in the proposal development team.

Relational factors explore professional and private relations between the members of the consortium and how these relations might affect proposal development. The results of the quantitative survey illustrate that the actors applying for H2020 and HEU funding perceive this group of factors as the most impactful when it comes to the success of MA project proposals. Thus, we can suggest that the success of a proposal is largely dependent on the skilful management of relations within the consortium. The relations that need to be managed have multiple angles – for example, there is a need to ensure that partners are in the right "place" in the consortium (in a place that allows consortia to benefit from partners' strengths), that they know what is expected from them, and that they feel comfortable with the people that surround them.

Successful management of partners is also linked to the characteristics of the project coordinator. It falls onto the shoulders of a coordinator to find the best ways to link partners, to make sure that partners feel heard, and that the consortium is moving towards a shared vision.

Figure 4. Importance and frequency of implementation of relational factors.

Good management of the consortium incorporates both good management practices as well as the use of technological innovations. For example, giving all partners access to all documents relevant to the proposal and ensuring that all of them have opportunities to comment on these materials, can ensure that all voices are heard, and stakeholders feel stronger ownership over the proposal. The same thinking can be achieved by pairing partners in smaller groups and asking smaller groups to produce parts of the documents. Several potential inclusion structures can be introduced in the process, such as ongoing and frequent communication, equality of voice, openness, and trust.

6.1 Timely start of partner recruitment and proposal development

A timely start of proposal writing is among the factors with very high perceived relevance. Initiating the proposal process early ensures adequate time for identifying the right partners, negotiating their roles, and fine-tuning the focus of the proposal. Additionally, this allows partners to actively engage

in the writing process and share their ideas. Most other factors discussed in this report presuppose that there is time allocated for the writing process. Thus, having sufficient time is also instrumental for engaging with most, if not all, of the factors of successful MA proposal writing. Yet, the survey also suggests that this resource is something emerging proposals might not have. Respondents suggest that often proposal development is not started early enough and because of that it has to be rushed, limiting the consortium's ability to properly benefit from MAA.

Respondents of qualitative interviews often mentioned that six months is the optimal period when one can put together a project proposal without rushing it. However, the same respondents also often shared their experience with good proposals that have been developed at the very last minute. As respondents explain – these proposals are built on a strong basis of knowledge by leaders who represent networks that can be easily integrated into the consortium as partners.

6.2 Attraction of partners with prior positive personal collaboration experience

This is one of the few factors in the quantitative survey where the perceived relevance of the factor mirrors the frequency it was observed. The benefits of having well-known partners in the consortium are obvious. It ensures at least some predictability in the proposal process, which can be sometimes difficult to control and which might be rather challenging. However, overreliance on existing networks of partners might lead to a situation where the consortium is not sufficiently diverse and does not truly capture the ethos of MAA. Furthermore, a consortium mainly benefiting from existing contacts might struggle to capture the full spectrum of competencies listed in the Call, as well as a lack of fresh insights most likely brought in by new partners.

6.3 Clear identification and appropriate and balanced distribution of partner roles, tasks, and responsibilities

Clear identification of partner roles, tasks, and responsibilities, which are distributed in an appropriate and balanced manner, is one of the factors deemed most relevant for a successful MA proposal (according to the survey). Furthermore,

“There is a great number of actors involving on MAA proposals, but SMEs are seen more from the national dissemination involvement point of view. If this is the way they are seen, then real MAA might not develop and become a strong asset of the project proposal.”

this is a factor with some of the highest discrepancies between the assessed relevance and frequency of actual occurrence, as revealed by the survey. A well-considered distribution of responsibilities during the proposal development ensures that partners have a clear perspective of what is expected of them. This means that partners are aware of the official role they have in the consortium and what expectations come with it. For example, it is common that work package leaders play a key role in pushing forward everything that is linked to the particular WP – including the methodology, description of the tasks, planned deliverables, etc. However, partners are also expected to contribute to the overall development of the proposal. Having a clear perspective on when one is expected to contribute and what is the nature of these contributions can ensure that partners do fulfil this task.

“I’ve rarely seen any MA project where the end-users are in the consortium! At the best, there are “associations or end-users” in the consortium (e.g. association of farmers from X region), and I think this is key, as these associations play the role of multipliers and discriminators towards the end-users (the farmers from the X region). In addition, these associations are the most appropriate actors to continue the development and exploitation of project outputs.”

From the perspective of the project coordinator, this means having a clear vision of how the roles are assigned to partners, how the work on the proposal is expected to progress, and when inputs from various partners will be needed. This also calls for a good

understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of each partner present in the consortium. The last point means that consortium leaders will know what content and in what form they can expect from the partners.

6.4 Decisive leadership and advancement of the proposal

The survey suggests that decisive leadership is the second most important factor determining the success of an MA project proposal. This does not come as a surprise. There is no single right way to write a project proposal, and thus the choice falls on the shoulders of the coordinator to steer the process and make sure that the consortium finds ways of co-creation and collaboration that suit this proposal group and are in line with the requirements of the particular Call. This task requires dedication and the ability to push the proposal forward even when partners struggle to allocate time to help advance it.

It also falls within the responsibility of the project leader to have the overall vision of how the final proposal should look and what shape the consortium

should take while also maintaining flexibility and space to integrate insights and needs of the partners in this vision. This might be a challenging task. On the one hand, there needs to be a possibility to discuss and improve the core vision guiding the proposal. Partners will raise their concerns and provide recommendations, and the project leader must keep an open mind and be willing to change the original vision if the proposed alternative is better. On the other hand, some partners might be looking for ways to bring their ambitions and agenda to the forefront while forgetting about the overall needs of the consortium. Or they might be proposing partners that are not the best choice for the proposal at hand. In these cases, it is up to the coordinator to make sure that the vision and the coherence of the proposal remain intact.

Making these decisions can be a demanding task of balancing the work on the project proposal with the management of the relations with and between consortium partners. This task will require both decisive action and transparency regarding the motivations behind the decisions made. Moreover, it should be considered that, while all involved partners may have some opinion or say on a matter at hand, it is the project coordinator who is responsible for making the final decision. Unfortunately, the survey also illustrates that there is a substantial gap between expectations and reality. Consequently, the assessment of the presence of decisive leadership in consortia is substantially lower than the perceived relevance of this factor.

6.5 Participatory, respectful internal communication and decision-making

There are a couple of aspects to the factor related to transparency, participation, and mutual respect. Firstly, and most importantly, transparent decision-making can ensure that all engaged partners feel that their ideas matter. This helps maintain shared ownership over the proposal. The workshop participants explained that it is typical that some partners dominate the consortium. There might be a broad list of reasons why this is the case such as forming of the core group of partners who have collaborated previously during the initial stages of the project or the division of responsibilities between the project partners proposed by the project coordinator. This domination might lead to a situation where some partners feel that their inputs are not welcomed and will not result in a real change in the proposal. This lowers their motivation to engage, consequently creating a situation where indeed just a handful of partners might be advancing the proposal. Such an approach can eventually lead to a successful proposal, yet it is not likely to lead to a successful MA proposal. Thus, **being transparent and ensuring**

equality of voice in the consortium is one of the keys to maintaining the interest of the partners. Transparency of decision-making processes can be fostered not only by addressing key questions for the whole consortium during the preparatory meetings but also by using online collaboration tools that let all partners become an integral part of the proposal development process. While all partners are responsible for taking part in the participatory process of project writing, it must also be noted that retaining the participatory approach and the sense that all opinions, including criticism, are being taken into consideration. This is the project coordinator's responsibility.

Secondly, Transparency and mutual respect can encourage partners who usually keep their ideas to themselves. Not all potential partners have the experience or energy to push forward and defend their ideas, but an encouraging environment can help these individuals to express their ideas and thus can facilitate that all types of stakeholders are taking an active part in the MA proposal development. However, this requires continuous effort to establish trust, promote openness, and efficient delegation of tasks.

6.6 Skilful alignment of the different personalities and cultures

The professionals invited to join the consortium are also individuals with diverse personalities and beliefs. Disregarding these peculiarities and not taking the influence of personality traits seriously can result in a situation where some partners are not engaged in proposal development at the level the coordinator might expect from them. This can hamper proposal development. However, it also creates room for conflicts and misunderstandings to emerge. A coordinator of a successful MA proposal needs to have a clear grasp of both the organisational and individual characteristics of partners invited to join the consortium.

7 SKILL-RELATED FACTORS

MA proposal development requires a broad set of skills. A proposal needs to deliver the competencies that have been listed in the Call. However, it also needs to show that the consortium can execute the proposed solution and ensure that the proposal presents the idea convincingly and coherently. **This designates aspects related to experiences, knowledge, and skills that allow partners to develop a successful MA proposal.**

The key skill-related factors to consider are:

- Strong leadership skills of the coordinator;
- Good professional skills of consortium partners;
- Consortium partners' mastery of technical and digital co-working solutions used during the proposal development process;
- Good transversal skills (such as communication, problem-solving, and time management skills) of consortium partners;
- Purposeful matching of tasks with partners' skills and competencies.

A successful consortium usually incorporates a variety of skills. This means that it must have a strategy on how to make sense of and work with this resource, including scrutinising the skills that are already represented by the consortia and identifying those that are missing. Furthermore, this assessment of available skills and those still needed have to simultaneously address two questions. Firstly, **does the consortium have the skillset needed to be successful and obtain the funding?** Secondly, **does the consortium have the skills needed to later execute the proposed work plan including the delivery of promised results?**

Potential partners bring diverse sets of skills and experiences to MA projects. This is one of the key characteristics of MAA - it envisions diversity. However, most often it requires extra effort for the consortium to benefit from the diversity of skills among the partners, and this process cannot be taken for granted. For instance, partners that might be the most prominent professionals in their field might lack some other crucial experience needed to successfully engage in MA cooperation. It is also possible that a partner does not have experience with working with large groups of stakeholders representing various backgrounds or has not worked with a particular type of Call before.

Such partners might lack the skills needed to develop a successful MA proposal tailored to this Call.

Partners might also struggle with mastering some of the methods (e.g. facilitation techniques for co-creation processes) or tools (e.g. IT applications) used to collaboratively work on the proposal. It is, therefore, a task for the coordinator and consortium as a whole to **work out solutions that will allow them to make the utmost use of and benefit from all the skills represented by partners and will enable them to apply these skills efficiently.** A good example is the division of tasks among the project partners. When accomplished in a participatory manner, it can be ensured that the partners are assigned tasks that allow them to use their skills most appropriately. Consequently, it also leads to each partner benefitting the most from the involvement.

Figure 5. Importance and frequency of implementation of skill-related factors.

The coordinator needs to **have a clear understanding of the needs of the consortium and how well they have been addressed.** Also, the coordinator **needs to be realistic about the competencies presented in the consortium** and whether the partners jointly will be able to deliver the expected results.

7.1 Strong leadership skills of the coordinator

According to the quantitative survey, this is among the top five factors in successful MA proposal development. The role of leadership has been stressed on several occasions during the survey, the interviews, and the workshop. Thus, we can conclude that having strong and skilled leadership is crucial for a successful MA project proposal. Finding the right coordinator might be a challenge and while one can expect that the idea to develop a proposal will come from the person who will later assume leadership. However, often individuals develop a proposal but will not lead a consortium. This might be because of their lack of experience, time, changing position or insufficient institutional support. This can lead to a situation where a consortium is gradually forming, yet without a dedicated leader. This might result in various hybrid solutions where official and unofficial leadership roles differ in the consortium. This just underlines that there is no one way how to build a consortium and manage an MA project. Each coordinating team or consortium will choose and define its path of MA proposal development. Choosing non typical ways how the consortium leadership is arranged can affect the collaboration, and result in a more challenging and time-consuming proposal writing. This might also result in unforeseen challenges for future project implementation.

In project proposals applying the MAA, the diversity of partners is typically high. While this aspect may be beneficial in many respects, it might also lead to more misunderstandings and potential conflicts. Moreover, there is a higher likelihood that at least some partners will lack the skills needed for a co creation process. It is expected that the coordinator will address these internal tensions. Because of this, the required leadership skills simultaneously cover multiple domains. The respondents of the qualitative interviews listed the required leadership skills and competencies of the coordinator as follows: **managing conflicts and unbalanced power relations, planning and steering the overall development of the proposal, day-to-day decision making, and developing and executing the vision of the proposal, understanding the diversity locked in the consortium.** On top of these management skills, the project coordinator to have **a deep understanding of the topic addressed in the proposal.** Finally, it is also expected that the coordinator will have **a supporting infrastructure** that allows them to address any challenges that might emerge during the writing process and can help deal with administrative burdens related to project proposals.

7.2 Good professional skills of consortium partners

The consortium structure should correspond to a particular vision that the MA proposal aims to communicate. This vision mirrors the challenge presented by the Call and the solution to the challenge envisioned by the project partners. It encompasses a set of tasks, and partners represent particular skills or characteristics needed to execute these tasks. Thus, in the perfect case scenario, partners are invited to join the consortium because of their ability to deliver something that allows the advancement of a particular aspect of the envisioned proposal. Having partners who are highly skilled in the issues the consortium addresses will help develop a competitive MA proposal that offers a meaningful vision of how to work with the issues listed in the Call. Therefore, the skill-related considerations once more raise the question of balance between well-known partners and newcomers; **how do we choose between tested partners who will deliver the expected result and new partners who might be better equipped to deal with issues raised in the Call?** On top of that, there is also the question of **how well the proposal text will highlight the skills and competencies represented by the consortium because the reviewers need to be convinced.** Considering the review process by external experts represents an additional dimension to the partner selection that might create new pitfalls in this MA proposal development process.

Finally, one must recognise that having highly professional partners does not automatically result in a successful MA proposal and that good professional skills do not automatically mean good collaboration skills. Even with the most professional team, the coordinator will still have to address the issues related to ensuring true collaboration and managing power relations within the consortium.

7.3 Consortium partners' mastery of technical and digital co-working solutions used during the proposal development process

Digital tools can help ensure that partners can work together more efficiently. Yet, the tools introduced to assist collaboration can either include or exclude partners from the co-creation process. The significance of the right tools has been stressed by multiple respondents during the interviews. Informants underlined that a successful MA proposal Calls for careful consideration of the **software used for joint writing, for holding meetings, and for supporting online discussions.** It has been suggested that partners representing different contexts might also differ in their preferences for and experiences with specific digital tools. Thus, it cannot be assumed that all partners will have the

necessary skills to engage the instruments proposed by the consortium. However, this is even more of a challenge for small local partners who might not have experience with these tools and thus a digital working culture might be completely new to them.

While all these potential challenges need to be considered, it should be also noted that in the quantitative survey, this was still perceived as one of the least relevant factors.

7.4 Good transversal skills of consortium partners such as communication, problem-solving, and time management skills

While partners are invited to join the consortium mostly for their professional competencies, they are also bringing into the consortium various other skills that might be valuable for a successful MA proposal. Benefiting from these skills will help the consortium to become more competitive.

7.5 Purposeful matching of tasks with partners' skills and competencies

Finally, the project coordinator should also consider how partners and their skills are bundled together in the MA proposal writing process. When bringing together a diverse set of people there is a risk of not benefiting from all the skills that are locked in the consortium or of unintentionally creating silos for different groups of partners. For example, by designating particular tasks to practice partners and others to academic partners the consortium risks reducing information exchange between the two groups. This might still lead to a project that gets funded, yet it will struggle to be able to successfully implement the MAA in the project. In other cases, some less experienced partners might struggle to find their way into the project and pairing them with more experienced partners can help fully benefit from the newcomer's skillset. Thus, an MA project proposal needs to **carefully consider how various types of actors are placed together and how tasks are distributed.**

8 INVENTORY OF KEY ISSUES EXPERIENCED BY DIFFERENT STAKEHOLDER GROUPS IN DEVELOPING MA PROJECT PROPOSALS

8.1 Issues experienced by science, policy, industry, and society stakeholders

The data collected in T3.1 of the PREMIERE project allows us to identify practical issues faced by representatives of specific groups of actors engaging in the MA project proposals. To clearly communicate the diversity of needs across the different groups we hereby present some key reconstructed issues (featured as artificially generated quotes, based on the obtained insights) along four stakeholder groups in line with the Quadruple Helix Model (i.e. science, policy, industry, and society).

Science actors must first and foremost learn a new way of viewing and structuring their academic work. Among the key issues as perceived by some representatives of this group one can mention the challenge of maintaining the moral code of academic integrity (i.e. acting in a way that is honest, fair, respectful and responsible), moving outside the comfort zone and expertise of traditional academic work, aligning the theoretical and applied needs in defining research questions, designing methodologies, and conducting research, as well as engaging in basic communication of science (to other non-academic partners) instead of digging deeper (see Table 5), delegating parts of scientific work to non-specialists, and ensuring an all-encompassing expertise across the different scales of inquiry at the expense of a more narrow specialisation.

Table 5: Issues faced by science actors.

1	<i>"I wonder how far we should follow the lead of farmers, policymakers and NGOs. Sometimes it feels that we should have an honest discussion on how we link the expectations of these partners and our <u>academic integrity</u>."</i>
2	<i>"Our department is mainly financed by international projects. This puts quite a lot of pressure on us. We would want to focus on academic research, but the financial burdens force us to <u>engage in all sorts of activities that we might not normally do</u>."</i>
3	<i>"We know exactly what knowledge gaps we need to address with our research. However, pursuing those goals is challenging when we are <u>constantly having to focus on the needs of stakeholders</u>."</i>

4	<i>"Our food technology department is unquestionably strong and highly competent. However, I believe that they are sometimes unable to fully realise their potential due to the expectation that <u>they should explain their vision to all consortium members</u>. They would undoubtedly be far more efficient if they were simply allowed to focus on their work."</i>
5	<i>"We have been taught how to conduct academic research and how to publish it in academic journals. However, we have not been taught how to <u>ensure the applicability of our research</u>."</i>
6	<i>"Now, with many of the partners in consortia being non-academics, we are facing new issues. In the past, all work was done by trained researchers. Now, some of that is passed to non-academic partners. With this shift theoretically we should focus more on clear delineation of who does what. However, this is not always the case, and we see <u>partners who lack the competencies to do certain tasks still doing them</u>. The same is true, of course, for academics. We often take on tasks now that we are not qualified or fully prepared to execute."</i>
7	<i>"We are all doing Living Labs now. We are expected to be successful with our LLs. Yet we are also expected to be able to say something about pan-European policies, broader trends, etc. Yet we cannot <u>do all these things simultaneously</u>. To properly do these things, we must work with a unique set of tools. Otherwise, the quality suffers."</i>
8	<i>I have been working with farmers for years. I know the problems they face, and I know how they would feel about this call. It is important to have real farmers as partners in the project. <u>Yet we do not need to bother them to get their opinions on all the issues we are discussing here</u>. We can give them space and ask for their help when the real work starts.</i>

For **policy** actors, making decisions can take substantially longer than for other groups due to cumbersome bureaucratic procedures and highly hierarchical organisational structures. Furthermore, in their work the policy actors must recognise and align with the broader strategic framework and policy agenda of their represented political unit and ensure practical outcomes from their involvement for the territory/community they are delegated to represent. Besides, the policy actors do not usually have project development seen as part and parcel of their job description which may preclude them from dedicated engagement throughout the proposal writing. They may also be more restricted in what they are allowed to do or not both technically and content-wise, coupled with the risks associated with political cycles and discontinuity of earlier efforts. A set of reconstructed issues faced by policy actors is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Issues faced by policy actors.

1	<i>“To make decisions, we must go through a rigid process. It is not that we can just decide to join the project - there are time-consuming steps we must follow. If we are invited as partners, the coordinators must recognise this.”</i>
2	<i>“If we join the project, it must be in line with the priorities set by our municipality. We are a public organisation, and we must follow the rules for public organisations. We can work together with project partners on the right framing of the issue. However, there must be a debate in the proposal-writing process that links the project's goals with the rhetoric recognised by our municipality.”</i>
3	<i>“The competencies required by the proposal coordinators were spread across several departments. Although we represent the same municipality, we are very different animals - each of us has our own staff, offices, agenda, internal cultures, etc., etc. It can be almost impossible to bring us together unless there is an attractive proposal or pressure from above. And even if we do come together, managing this collaboration can be a daunting task in itself.”</i>
4	<i>“Thinking ahead and getting involved in new projects is interesting and exciting. But we also have our <u>day-to-day responsibilities</u>. Maybe some of my colleagues have time built into their salaries just to pursue new projects, but certainly not me - I really have to look for designated moments when I can work on the proposal. So I would appreciate if other partners and proposal coordinators were efficient and prepared when we discuss the proposal.”</i>
5	<i>“They were using programmes that were not used in our department, so we had no experience with them. Also, we <u>cannot install new software on the government computers</u>. Fortunately, after talking to the coordinator, we realised that the software they were using could be used online and was very simple.”</i>
6	<i>“Today, we are interested in making green public procurement a reality. We are working to ensure that the solutions we have in mind are actually put into practice. However, we have local elections next year and I cannot honestly say that <u>the new decision-makers will have the same view on these issues</u>.”</i>
7	<i>“There is already a map of abandoned sites developed for our city. There is also a map that lists areas of high urban biodiversity, some projects that focus on water recycling, and many other things. We are not interested in developing yet another version of these things. <u>We want to make meaningful progress</u>.”</i>

The **industry** partners, in turn, are searching for practical, down-to-earth solutions that could help introduce tailored innovations in the activities the given enterprise is engaged in rather than some more generic ones or ones that are not relevant for their specific needs. Often these enterprises have limited experience with proposal writing or collaboration with academic or other types of actors, and they may lack the skills, capacity, and the more holistic

view of the topic for efficiently leading an MA consortium. Furthermore, enterprises might have limited access to or knowledge of networks potentially applying for MA project funding. Due to their business interests, they are much more cautious with open sharing of data and knowledge that might come in conflict with open access policies guiding funders and other types of partners. A set of reconstructed issues faced by industry is presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Issues faced by industry actors.

1	<i>“We joined the consortium because <u>we thought the topic will help us a lot with our water issues</u>, but later we found out that the scientific team only wanted to focus on drip irrigation.”</i>
2	<i>“The wording of the two pager they sent to us was so policy-focused that <u>we could not really understand what they wanted from our group</u>.”</i>
3	<i>“We had a seed funding budget and organised a meeting. We could even pay for the travel of the practice partners involved. That was useful to <u>disentangle the call topic text with the different perspectives in the room</u>.”</i>
4	<i>“We are setting up our Living Lab with farmers and value chain businesses in the organic agri-food-industry in our region, but we need a project that helps us to do so. We have different topics to work on, but nobody is asking us to join their proposal consortium. <u>We have no idea how to find a coordinator who might be looking for an initiative like ours</u>.”</i>
5	<i>“We participated in a brokerage event that was organised by a Brussels-based organisation, but <u>we didn’t meet any coordinators</u>. Only others like us were there which were looking for coordinators we could join.”</i>
6	<i>“We are in contact with a university, but we do not know what they are expecting from us when we join the group. <u>What do they want us to do?</u>”</i>
7	<i>“<u>Data protection is a major issue for us</u>. We do not want to share the new data with our competitors. We rely on data and information ownership to secure our niche market ideas.”</i>
8	<i>“<u>IPR issues</u> have been settled during the proposal phase. We had put it all into a written agreement. Our lawyer also had a look at it. I hope we will be safe.”</i>
9	<i>“<u>We have no time for any management work</u>. This needs to be done by the academic partners. We just have no staff for any extra organisational tasks. However, we are eager to work on the piloting of our new tool. If we had two more test sides in other areas, that would be great.”</i>

Civil society is represented by a great variety of organisations – they differ in the scale they operate, their goals, budgets, etc. Yet, many can be limited in their financial and human resources at hand, thus requiring extra guidance

and support. Civil society organisations might also find challenging to link their specific needs and interests to the broader framing of the problem statements as posed by the Call, as well as align their envisaged activities and motivations with the ethos of project logic, formal requirements and jargon. Some of the issues these organisations might face are reconstructed in Table 8.

Table 8: Issues faced by civic society.

1	<p><i>“Our daily operations are maintained by two people – my colleague and me. We work together as a great team. Yet, because we have limited resources, we need to be our own bookkeepers, communication specialists, funding experts, and even janitors if that's what's required. Unfortunately, <u>we don't have the resources to hire anybody else, so it's all on our shoulders.</u> We're really hoping that this project will help us and cover a salary for a colleague who could work explicitly with the problems of young female farmers. So yeah, we are highly motivated to participate. It is just that the time that we can allocate to the proposal is very limited.”</i></p>
2	<p><i>“We've got some experience of working on projects – last year we were lucky enough to get some local funding to help cover some of our costs. But <u>this is our first time working on an international project proposal, so it's all very new to us.</u> It's been a bit overwhelming at times, to be honest! I think we would have dropped out of the consortium if it hadn't been for the coordinator. She's been a great help. We have this agreement that, whenever we have questions, we can chat with her administrative department.”</i></p>
3	<p><i>“When I read the call, I had to ask myself, “Is it for us?” I understand that the issues raised in the call are very real and might be relevant somewhere. However, to be honest, <u>I don't see that these broad issues represent what we experience here on the ground.</u> We are struggling with very basic, very real challenges in our communities, and we need to focus on those.”</i></p>
4	<p><i>“I must admit, I've never really understood the point of producing deliverables and other documents. We've always strived to have a real impact, and that's what matters to us. <u>It's so wonderful to see the community thriving, and it doesn't matter to us if we can put it on paper.</u>”</i></p>
5	<p><i>“We are a large, international organisation with regional offices all around the world. We receive invitations to join various proposals every week, so we must be selective. If a project wants us on board, its representatives must be precise when they approach us. <u>They must demonstrate how the application aligns with our existing activities and how it will benefit us.</u>”</i></p>
6	<p><i>“I was at the consortium meeting yesterday and <u>realised that I don't understand what everybody is talking about.</u> It was about living labs, and I didn't feel confident enough to ask what these are. So, I was sitting there not being able to contribute to the discussion.”</i></p>

8.2 Scrutinising the quadruple helix

Quadruple helix is probably among the most recognised analytical tools used to distinguish between the different needs of stakeholder groups. This is also the tool that has been used to structure the data gathered in the PREMIERE project. Interestingly, while we expect to see a clear delineation between various stakeholder groups and have sought to highlight the specificity of each group in the section above, the overall reflection on survey and interview answers in the broader PREMIERE context shows significant similarities between the needs of these groups. Such shared needs indicate that there might be limitations as to how far the approach can be successfully applied - identifying specific partners based on their background may not be the most useful framework to support them. We need to scrutinise other organisational characteristics of different stakeholders to capture the qualities that differentiate between those in the context of MA proposal development.

We suggest that individual partner needs, limitations, and capacities largely cease to exist when the process of forming a consortium is completed since those individual factors should be integrated into the conditions of the consortium. Thus, if the focus is on the partners, they can look very different one from another. However, once the focus is shifted to a consortium, the individual differences tend to vanish behind the very similar responses they should trigger in the consortium. From that point forward the individual consortium partners move on as a collective, bound by shared goals and definition of success, irrespective of their individual (stakeholder-group) backgrounds. While their individual competencies may have secured them a position at the table, it is their transversal (MAA) skills that bind them in going forward; when communication issues arise, the consortium as a collective suffers the associated risks. Alternatively, when an individual consortium partner finds a tool or instrument to facilitate a need (for example, a shared online whiteboard to collaborate), this benefits all consortium members.

Since the transition from an individual actor to a collective consortium happens as part of the process of developing a proposal, identifying MA partners through the lens of their respective stakeholder background is only useful prior to consortium formation (in the context of PREMIERE, focused on offering MAA support during the entire proposal development phase). In fact, giving up the individual perspective in favour of the collective one may be key to the success of an MAA proposal, as trust, shared goals, and mutual stakes are essential to co-creative collaborations. This, of course, must happen while

retaining the benefits of the diversity of perspectives and experiences a multi-actor consortium has to offer.

This is not to say that the stakeholder group's perspective is not relevant at all. In fact, in the systemic context of Horizon Calls the dynamics between different stakeholder groups are actively observed and potentially reinforced by the Calls. The perspective on/disposition towards distinct stakeholder groups may therefore be essential to overcome, to reach the common ground necessary for successful MAA implementation. It may even explain the positive feedback on the MAMY roleplaying game developed as part of WP4 efforts, in which these different stakeholder groups are somewhat caricatured to facilitate open discussions. Substantiating this reflection and offering solutions within the context of PREMIERE may warrant additional investigations.

Finally, data suggests that there are other relevant characteristics of organisations that might have a more prominent effect on partners' ability to successfully participate in MA proposal writing. The key factor to be mentioned here is **the size of the organisation**. Time and time again we observe that for larger organisations it is easier to overcome any hurdles related to proposal writing and that the larger organisations have more power to push for their perceived agenda. Directly linked to the size is the question of whether the organisation can maintain **staff that specialises** in working with international project proposals similar to those submitted for Horizon programmes. On the one hand, we have to scrutinise who has a better overview of the lexicon and expectations coming from the programme in general. However, on the other hand, this is also a question of which are the support programmes of choice for different types of stakeholders that they choose to specialise in.

9 CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

9.1 What is success for MA proposals?

Should we consider the success of multi-actor (MA) proposals differently than we would in the case of any other proposal? The answer is – yes, we should. This is because the networks of actors forming a consortium for the MA proposal are linked to particular challenges as well as specific expectations. The obvious goal everybody representing any consortium is driven by is to be granted funding to execute the proposed idea. However, the data collected in the PREMIERE project illustrates that there are other notable interpretations on what is the right answer to the question – what a success for MA proposals is. This might seem to be a philosophical nuance relevant only to those looking for ways to complicate simple things. However, the reality is that the multi-actor approach (MAA) envisions a particular end-goal of projects as well as processes leading to these projects. Thus, if compared to a project conducted by just researchers, entrepreneurs or any other stakeholder group, MAA should be approached slightly differently.

The proposal development stage of potential projects stops with the submission of the proposal. However, the real nature of the proposal can be observed if the proposal is funded, and the ideas worked into the proposal must be executed. One can say that in the execution stage, you reap what you sowed. For MA proposals, if one wants to be able to execute the project that has been envisioned, it is crucial to **establish practices allowing to work together between different groups already at the proposal stage**. There needs to be clarity, on how the collaboration will work. Ensuring successful collaboration starts already at the proposal development phase and can be facilitated in various ways.

First, it is essential to make sure that during the proposal development phase trust is built and partners' experiences and skills are critically assessed. Second, the project coordinator or the core group of partners must ensure that partners know what they are expected to deliver and that they have the resources to do it. Some in-depth interviews explicitly stated that often the proposal is developed by a small group of core partners. For example, if researchers take too much lead and forget to consult other groups engaged, this might lead to a lack of sense of ownership in other groups that, in turn, might lead to an unwillingness to invest time and effort in advancing the proposal. This can result in a situation where some partners do not know what

they are committing themselves to in the project, leading to possible further issues in the project development stage.

A successful proposal finds a way to align the focus of the call with the interests/ ambitions of partners. The calls for proposals follow their agenda and will not always represent the interests of all partners on the ground. While sometimes partners are just looking for funding, in the perfect world, potential partners have their vision of what they want to achieve and where they want to go. A successful proposal manages to align these two realities.

Finally, it is also worth noting, that a successful process of building the consortium and drafting the proposal does not always equate with a successful process of project implementation if funded. Some informants of the in-depth interviews suggested that even a smooth proposal development stage can lead to less successful project implementation than expected.

9.2 How to write a successful MA proposal?

There is **no one right way** how to develop a successful MA project proposal. The work on a proposal starts well before the actual writing process. Firstly, partners have to choose what calls they want to work with and with what type of partners they are willing to collaborate. The considerations linked to this choice can differ:

- It is expected that one will **choose projects that correspond to the organisation's vision**, strategy and the skills locked in the organisation.
- **However, not everybody can choose.** Some organisations, **financially dependent** on project funding, will feel the pressure to be less critical regarding what projects they will join. Furthermore, some partners will have **limited entry points** to join the emerging consortia.
- Some partners are willing to go the extra mile to ensure that their interests are captured in the project calls. One way to do it is to **communicate your ideas directly to the funding body (European Commission).**

Depending on the call, each consortium will have its own unique and most suitable way to be built and managed. It can be unlocked through a good understanding and alignment of the call and ambitions, skills, experiences, and

resources locked in the consortium. A successful proposal needs to have the following:

- A **vision** of the expected results of the project.

Partners need to agree on what the results that they will be working towards are. An important prerequisite of a successful MA project proposal is the **alignment of interests since** projects adapting MAA bring together actors representing different sectors and different ways of thinking.

- A **strategy** for how the proposal development process will be organised and advanced.

The consortium needs to have a preliminary plan on how it intends to move forward. During the interviews, respondents shared experiences of proposals that were developed over a period of six months while some other proposals were assembled comparatively quickly in a period of just a few months. However, what united all of them was a structured approach to putting the proposal together. For instance, there might be a core group of partners working more deliberately on the development of work areas and work packages. In this case, they would often develop a coherent strategy to involve other members of the consortium in the proposal writing process, such as by asking for structured feedback and comments, as well as developing a system how all partners could select the tasks that they would like to be working on during the project implementation stage. In general, respondents suggest starting to plan as early as possible.

A suitable timeframe is crucial in MAA proposal development. An approach that is sensitive to partners' needs requires time. Yet, often, the idea of writing a proposal comes later than it would be optimal for considering different partners' needs thus limiting the possibility of any reflection, discussions or strategy.

- An ongoing **critical reflection** of the proposal writing process.

Most consortia have at least some internal structures to ensure that there is a critical debate regarding the overall process of how the proposal is advanced. However, many proposals also incorporate additional aspects when external evaluators are invited to share their thoughts on the emerging proposal. The evaluators' feedback increases the chance of getting the project funded, as evaluators know the expectations of the evaluation panel.

9.3 General reflections on the results

1. Constant gap between relevance and presence. The added value of the obtained results seems to be the non-compliance of the highly assessed importance of individual factors with the perceived (almost constantly) lower level of their actual presence in practice. The only factors that were assessed higher on the level of presence than their importance were related to (1) presence of previous experience with preparation and implementation of international projects, which in a way shows that such experience matters but is not deemed of utmost importance, and (2) early signing of internal consortium agreements, which might imply that at least at the stage of proposal development these formal issues, which do not make much difference for proposal submission and evaluation, do not make much difference, though might be needed in the long run.

2. Most notable gap between relevance and presence. For some factors the gap between the perceived relevance and presence in the proposal development process where notably higher than the average gap. These factors represent an area where the effort to initiate change might bring the highest yield. The top five factors with the highest gap are the following: (1) Decisive leadership and advancement of the overall proposal development; (2) Consortium partners' commitment to devote time and effort to proposal writing; (3) Clear identification and appropriate and balanced distribution of partner roles, tasks, and responsibilities; (4) Timely start of partner recruitment and proposal development; (5) Consortium size is kept at the level that allows maintaining an inclusive discussion.

3. The most relevant factors. The results of the survey show that the top 5 most highly ranked factors (with an average score of 4,5+) in terms of their importance across all factor groups have to do with a dedicated interest in the proposal and a good understanding of the requirements of the specific call, along with strong leadership in tandem with wise delegation of tasks between the partners.

4. Some demographic factors affected the perception of the importance of assessed factors. The survey illustrates that age and project experience affect the perception of some of the factors. For example, older respondents and respondents with more experience rate the following factors as less important: "Consortium partners' interest in the project's anticipated practical output"; "Consortium partners have the administrative, financial, and staff capacity to

work on the proposal”, “Good transversal skills (such as communication, problem-solving, time management skills) of consortium partners”, and “Purposeful matching of tasks with partners’ skills and competencies”. Gender also affects some factors. For example, male respondents rate the following factors as less important: “Consortium partners’ willingness to collaborate with other types of multi-actor partners in the proposal development”, and “Transparent, participatory, and mutually respectful internal communication and decision-making”.

9.4 Methodological considerations

The data that has been gathered under T3.1 raises some methodological questions that might be relevant for future research.

1. Choice of methods. There might be additional factors at play that have not been captured by any of the different methods employed in this exercise and which might need a different conceptual framework and methods of inquiry. Yet we believe that the employment of a diverse set of methods and triangulation of findings have captured an important share of those factors that are at play in defining the level of success of the MA proposal development process.

2. What are the most suitable methods for this exercise? Some factors have been assessed differently in different data sources. Most notably this can be observed in Contextual factors are considered. While during the workshops and in-depth interviews these were presented as extremely relevant factors, this sentiment was not mirrored in the survey. It could signify, that not all factors can be measured with the same methods. For example, the role of contextual factors might be easier to appreciate with qualitative methods.

3. How things are and how we would want them to be! The differences in assessment across different methods could also signify that respondents might have been assessing different things. In the quantitative survey respondents very explicitly were asked to assess the significance of the factors. It is possible, that the data obtained with the qualitative methods unconsciously also captures how things should be. This means that while some factors might not be instrumental in coming up with a successful MA proposal, in general, in an ideal world we would want these factors to be considered and addressed. Again, the Contextual factors might serve as an illustration.

4. Randomisation of factors. On the methodological note, it could also be the case that given the fact that in the survey factors were presented in five groups of factors rather than in a more random order, the individual ranking might have been performed vis-a-vis other factors in those groups rather than over the whole spectrum. Such an alternative approach when factors are not presented by only afterwards analysed with their attribution to a specific factor group might have generated slightly different results.

10 REFERENCES

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11 ANNEXES

11.1 Interview guidelines

Guiding questions for 13 in-depth/qualitative interviews with project participants for the rapid assessment of good practices (and failings) in multi-actor proposal preparation (T3.1)

[Briefly tell about the project and the aim of this exercise.]

INTRODUCTORY QUESTIONS

At the level of the organisation:

- Please briefly tell me about the **organisation** you are currently affiliated with and your professional role in it?
- What **project funding schemes** does your organisation usually participate in and in what capacity? What is the role of Horizon funding in your organisation? Since when and how often have you been engaged in Horizon consortia?

At the individual level:

- Could you please briefly outline the duration and intensity of your **overall personal experience** in engaging in EU-funded work as well as developing H2020/Horizon Europe multi-actor project proposals?
- Could you please recall **one more memorable recent proposal** that you were personally involved in?
- What was your **formal role** in this proposal (coordinator, partner; WP/task lead, no leadership function)?
- Did the project manage to be **funded** (if already evaluated)?

We will now focus more on this **specific experience**, going into more detail through the process of building the consortium, writing the proposal, and dealing with the administrative and technical management of this process.

- Why is it the most memorable proposal?

1. BUILDING A CONSORTIUM

- What were the main challenges related to building the consortium?
or
- Can you please recall how and why the proposal was **initiated** and by whom? Who formed the initial groups of proposers?
- How were **partners** identified and contacted?

- What went **particularly well** in the consortium-building? What would you **do differently** next time and why?
 - Were there any **drop-out partners** in the consortium building process? If yes, do you know the reasons for that?
 - Did you get the feeling that some partners came in **too late or too early** in the process of consortium building? If so, which type of partners were these?

2. WRITING THE PROPOSAL

- What were the main challenges related to writing the consortium?
or
- How would you generally characterise the **writing process** of the proposal? Were all partners equally engaged/ motivated?
- What were the **main points of discussion** during proposal-writing (e.g. WP structure, distribution of tasks, types of deliverables)? Where the ideas of all partners listened to?
- How was the **distribution of roles** and responsibilities negotiated/decided among the consortium partners?
- Were there any **specific points of frustration** you recall from this process of writing the proposal?

3. ADMINISTRATIVE AND TECHNICAL MANAGEMENT

- What were the main administrative challenges related to the proposal?
or
- Were there any **issues related to the administrative and/or technical side** of drafting and submitting the application (e.g. filling in Part A, dealing with the tender platform, finding the right information)?
- If so, which types of partners found this difficult? Why do you think that is? How did the consortium deal with partners that found this challenging?
- In case you had already been engaged in drafting multi-actor projects prior to this proposal, were there any tips and tricks from this former experience that allowed you to engage more successfully in this process?

CLOSING QUESTIONS

- What is the **main lesson** you've learned for yourself from your prior experience in engaging in proposals for multi-actor projects and which you take into consideration when engaging in writing new project proposals?

Would you be willing to **share your experience** in future PREMIERE activities, like short videos, webinars or live sessions?

11.2 Template of the online survey

Success factors in developing multi-actor project proposals

Thank you for agreeing to participate in the survey!

This survey aims to improve the understanding of which factors are key elements while preparing successful “multi-actor” (MA) project proposals. “Multi-actor” refers to the “multi-actor approach” (MAA) which is currently a requirement in around 40% of EU Horizon Europe Cluster 6: “Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment” calls for proposals. The MAA implies that the project consortium must consist of different partners engaging in a multidirectional exchange: the ones needing a solution to their problem (end-users) and the ones who can provide the necessary practical, scientific or other complementary knowledge or skill to solve the problem. This requires bringing together actors with different yet complementary forms of expertise, skills and knowledge.

The survey focuses on your experience as a project partner with the MAA during the proposal development stage. You will be presented with a list of possible factors related to the development of a MA project proposal and asked which ones you find most relevant during a MA project proposal process.

Answering the questions will not require more than 20 minutes of your time. The survey is anonymous and the answers you provide will be used only in aggregated form. The data will be stored according to the best data management practices.

This survey is part of the PREMIERE project (“Preparing multi-actor projects in a co-creative way”) funded under the European Union (EU) programme Horizon Europe (Grant agreement ID: 101086531). PREMIERE aims to strengthen the multi-actor approach by supporting the development of more socially relevant, coherent, and well-prepared project proposals. This includes all aspects related to the identification of suitable partners, building the project partnership, designing the work plan, and negotiating budget distribution. To learn more about the project, please visit the project’s website <https://premiere-multiactor.eu/>.

If you have any questions regarding the survey, please contact please contact Mikelis Grivins at the BALTIC STUDIES CENTRE (mikelis.grivins@bscresearch.lv).

Success factors in developing multi-actor project proposals

*** Do you personally have any current or former experience with engaging in EU Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe multi-actor (MA) project proposals (irrespective of whether submitted and/or funded)?**

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Success factors in developing multi-actor project proposals

*** In the development of how many EU MA proposals have you personally been involved?**

I have participated in the preparation of...

- ...one EU MA project proposal
- ...two EU MA project proposals
- ...three or more EU MA project proposals
- I have not participated in the preparation of EU MA projects proposals

Success factors in developing multi-actor project proposals

*** In what type of EU MA actions have you participated and/or aimed to participate?**

You can select more than one answer.

- Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
- Innovation Action (IA)
- Coordination and Support Action (CSA)
- I do not know
- Other (please specify)

*** Under which EU funding programme have you applied and/or aimed to apply for MA project funding?**

- Horizon 2020
- Horizon Europe
- Both
- Don't know

*** Thinking about the most recent EU MA project proposal you personally were engaged in, please indicate what was your (i.e. your organisation's) formal role in the proposal?**

I (i.e. my organisation) was...

In case of several simultaneous roles, please select the one with the highest degree of responsibility.

- Coordinator
- WP lead/ co-lead
- Task lead/ co-lead
- Non-lead partner
- Administrator
- Consultant
- Associated partner
- Don't know
- Other (please specify)

*** What country do/would you (your organisation) typically represent in the EU MA project proposals?**

If you have been applying and/or intending to apply for funding from several countries, please indicate the country you were representing in your most recently developed EU MA project proposal.

*** What type of beneficiary profile do/would you typically represent in EU MA project proposals?**

If you have been applying and/or intending to apply for funding as part of different types of organisations, please indicate the type of organisation you were representing in your most recent EU MA project proposal.

- Government/Policy
- Science/Academia
- Industry/Business
- Society/Community
- Other (please specify)

*** What is the main area of activity of the organisation you represented in the most recent EU MA project proposal?**

Please briefly describe:

(give a short description such as, for example, Farmers' organisation focusing on the rights of small farms; Food producer working in the meat industry; Tech giant developing novel soil quality monitoring instruments; etc.)

*** What is the size of the organisation you represent(ed) in the most recent EU MA project proposal?**

- micro (<10 employees)
- small (10-49 employees)
- medium (50-250 employees)
- large (>250 employees)
- don't know

Success factors in developing multi-actor project proposals

International and national project funders increasingly request project applicants to demonstrate that the submitted funding applications adopt the multi-actor approach. The MAA implies that the project consortium must consist of different partners engaging in a multidirectional exchange: the ones needing a solution to their problem (end-users) and the ones who can provide the necessary practical, scientific or other complementary knowledge or skill to solve the problem.

*** Which of the following statements best captures your thoughts regarding the growing popularity of MAA in Horizon Europe Cluster 6: "Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment" projects?**

- I fully support the funders' request to adopt the multi-actor approach.
- I support the funders' request to adopt the multi-actor approach, yet there should be exceptions.
- I do not support the funders' request to adopt the multi-actor approach, yet some projects might benefit from it.
- I completely oppose the funders' request to adopt the multi-actor approach.
- No answer

Success factors in developing multi-actor project proposals

Factors of a successful MA proposal

While writing a proposal, project partners must deal with various motivational, contextual, relational, skill-related, and predefined factors. The survey will now list factors that might be important during a multi-actor proposal development. Please provide your personal assessment of the importance of each of these

factors for developing a successful multi-actor project proposal.

For this assessment - please do not just support the claims that are generally considered to be true. Instead, use your personal experience and considerations to make the assessment.

Please keep in mind that the survey addresses the proposal development stage. Thus, during the assessment process consider only the experiences you have had and/or are having with the MA proposal development.

Success factors in developing multi-actor project proposals						
Assessment of Motivational factors						
<p>Developing a multi-actor project proposal requires substantial effort, hence one must be highly motivated to fully engage in the process. The practices common in the consortium can either increase or reduce the willingness/ motivation of partners to become involved in the consortium and engage in the proposal development process. We call these factors that can shape partner motivation - “motivational” factors. Below a set of motivational factors is listed.</p> <p>* When it comes to developing a successful multi-actor project proposal, how important, based on your personal experience, each of these factors is? For the assessment please use the scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is “Not at all important” and 5 is “Extremely important”.</p>						
	1 - not at all important	2 - somewhat important	3 - important	4 - very important	5 - extremely important	Don't know
Consortium partners' interest in the call topic and/or project idea	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Consortium partners' feeling of ownership over the proposal development	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Consortium partners' interest in the project's anticipated practical output	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Consortium partners' commitment to devote time and effort to proposal writing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Consortium partners' willingness to collaborate with other types of multi-actor partners in the proposal development	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*** Based on your personal experience, how often each of these factors can be observed in practice? For the assessment please use the scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is "Never" and 5 is "Always".**

	1 - never	2 - seldom	3 - sometimes	4 - often	5 - always	Don't know
Consortium partners are interested in the call topic and/or project idea	<input type="radio"/>					
Consortium partners are feeling ownership over the proposal development	<input type="radio"/>					
Consortium partners are interested in the project's anticipated practical output	<input type="radio"/>					
Consortium partners are committed to devote time and effort to proposal writing	<input type="radio"/>					
Consortium partners are willing to collaborate with other types of multi-actor partners in the proposal development	<input type="radio"/>					

Do you have any comments after assessing the motivational factors?

Please provide any general thoughts or any suggestions on the factors listed above, incl. regarding potentially missing important motivational factors!

Success factors in developing multi-actor project proposals

Assessment of Contextual factors

Organisations operate in a specific context. When these organisations join a consortium, they bring this context with them creating a situation where the consortium must actively engage with questions related to the diversity of partners. We call these different contextual aspects that can shape the way a proposal is developed - "contextual" factors. Below a set of contextual factors is listed.

*** When it comes to developing a successful multi-actor project proposal, how important, based on your personal experience, each of the listed factors is? For the assessment please use the scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is "Not at all important" and 5 is "Extremely important".**

	1 - not at all important	2 - somewhat important	3 - important	4 - very important	5 - extremely important	Don't know
Consortium partners have the administrative, financial, and staff capacity to work on the proposal	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Consortium partners have previous general experience with preparation and implementation of international projects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Within the consortium there is an understanding of and willingness to adapt to the different national contexts partners represent	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Within the consortium there is an understanding of and willingness to adapt to the diverse profiles and cultures of partners' organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Project coordinator understands and engages with regional/national and organisation-specific budget setting (incl. salary rates)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Consortium size is kept at the level that allows maintaining an inclusive discussion	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*** Based on your personal experience, how often each of these factors can be observed in practice? For the assessment please use the scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is "Never" and 5 is "Always".**

	1 - never	2 - seldom	3 - sometimes	4 - often	5 - always	Don't know
Consortium partners have the administrative, financial, and staff capacity to work on the proposal	<input type="radio"/>					
Consortium partners have previous general experience with preparation and implementation of international projects	<input type="radio"/>					
Within the consortium there is an understanding of and willingness to adapt to the different national contexts partners represent	<input type="radio"/>					
Within the consortium there is an understanding of and willingness to adapt to the diverse profiles and cultures of partners' organisations	<input type="radio"/>					
Project coordinator understands and engages with regional/national and organisation-specific budget setting (incl. salary rates)	<input type="radio"/>					
Consortium size is kept at the level that allows maintaining an inclusive discussion	<input type="radio"/>					

Do you have any comments after assessing the contextual factors?

Please provide any general thoughts on the factors listed above or any suggestions, incl. regarding potentially missing important context-sensitive factors!

Assessment of Relational factors

Proposal development requires continuous decision-making by the coordinator. Decisions made must facilitate the efficiency of the consortium’s work on the proposal. However, these decisions must also be attentive to the diversity of partners gathered in the consortium. We call factors reflecting issues related to the decision-making processes - “relational” factors. Below a set of relational factors is listed.

*** When it comes to developing a successful multi-actor project proposal, how important, based on your personal experience, each of these factors is? For the assessment please use the scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is “Not at all important” and 5 is “Extremely important”.**

	1 - not at all important	2 - somewhat important	3 - important	4 - very important	5 - extremely important	Don't know
Timely start of partner recruitment and proposal development	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Attraction of partners with prior positive personal collaboration experience	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clear identification and appropriate and balanced distribution of partner roles, tasks, and responsibilities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Decisive leadership and advancement of the overall proposal development	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Transparent, participatory, and mutually respectful internal communication and decision-making	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Skillful alignment of different personalities engaged in the proposal development team	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*** Based on your personal experience, how often each of these factors can be observed in practice? For the assessment please use the scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is “Never” and 5 is “Always”.**

	1 - never	2 - seldom	3 - sometimes	4 - often	5 - always	Don't know
Timely start of partner recruitment and proposal development	<input type="radio"/>					
Attraction of partners with prior positive personal collaboration experience	<input type="radio"/>					
Clear identification and appropriate and balanced distribution of partner roles, tasks, and responsibilities	<input type="radio"/>					
Decisive leadership and advancement of the overall proposal development	<input type="radio"/>					
Transparent, participatory, and mutually respectful internal communication and decision-making	<input type="radio"/>					
Skillful alignment of different personalities engaged in the proposal development team	<input type="radio"/>					

Do you have any comments after assessing the relational factors?

Please provide any general thoughts on the factors listed above or any suggestions, incl. regarding potentially missing important relational factors!

Success factors in developing multi-actor project proposals

Assessment of Skill-related factors

Multi-actor approach brings together consortium partners with diverse sets of skills, experiences, and knowledge. Issues related to skill management we call “skill-related” factors. Below a set of skill-related factors is listed.

*** When it comes to developing a successful multi-actor project proposal, how important, based on your personal experience, each of these factors is? For the assessment please use the scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is “Not at all important” and 5 is “Extremely important”.**

	1 - not at all important	2 - somewhat important	3 - important	4 - very important	5 - extremely important	Don't know
Strong leadership skills of the coordinator	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Good professional skills of consortium partners	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Consortium partners' mastery of technical and digital co-working solutions used during the proposal development process	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Good transversal skills (such as communication, problem-solving, time management skills) of consortium partners	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Purposeful matching of tasks with partners' skills and competencies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*** Based on your personal experience, how often each of these factors can be observed in practice? For the assessment please use the scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is “Never” and 5 is “Always”.**

	1 - never	2 - seldom	3 - sometimes	4 - often	5 - always	Don't know
Strong leadership skills of the coordinator	<input type="radio"/>					
Good professional skills of consortium partners	<input type="radio"/>					
Consortium partners' mastery of technical and digital co-working solutions used during the proposal development process	<input type="radio"/>					
Good transversal skills (such as communication, problem-solving, time management skills) of consortium partners	<input type="radio"/>					
Purposeful matching of tasks with partners' skills and competencies	<input type="radio"/>					

Do you have any comments after assessing the skill-related factors?

Please provide any general thoughts on the factors listed above or any suggestions, incl. regarding potentially missing important skill-related factors!

Success factors in developing multi-actor project proposals

Assessment of Predefined factors

While developing a multi-actor project proposal, some of the aspects the consortium must work with cannot be changed without a strong justification or substantial effort. We call these factors “Predefined”. Below a set of predefined factors is listed.

*** When it comes to developing a successful multi-actor project proposal, how important, based on your personal experience, each of the listed factors is? For the assessment please use the scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is “Not at all important” and 5 is “Extremely important”.**

	1 - not at all important	2 - somewhat important	3 - important	4 - very important	5 - extremely important	Don't know
Good understanding of the administrative, budgetary, reporting and evaluation criteria of the call	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Purposeful selection of partners focusing on the partner profiles listed in the call	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Deep understanding of the objectives, scope and expected impacts of the call	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The skills represented by the consortium mirror the skillset described in the call	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Time allocated to work out which are the right partners and the right focus for the proposal already in the early stages of proposal development	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The internal formal consortium agreements (e.g. Memorandum of Understanding, Non-disclosure Agreement, Intellectual Property Rights Agreement) are developed and signed already at the stage of proposal development	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*** Based on your personal experience, how often each of these factors can be observed in practice? For the assessment please use the scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is "Never" and 5 is "Always".**

	1 - never	2 - seldom	3 - sometimes	4 - often	5 - always	Don't know
Good understanding of the administrative, budgetary, reporting and evaluation criteria of the call	<input type="radio"/>					
Purposeful selection of partners focusing on the partner profiles listed in the call	<input type="radio"/>					
Deep understanding of the objectives, scope and expected impacts of the call	<input type="radio"/>					
The skills represented by the consortium mirror the skillset described in the call	<input type="radio"/>					
Time allocated to work out which are the right partners and the right focus for the proposal already in the early stages of proposal development	<input type="radio"/>					
The internal formal consortium agreements (e.g. Memorandum of Understanding, Non-disclosure Agreement, Intellectual Property Rights Agreement) are developed and signed already at the stage of proposal development	<input type="radio"/>					

Do you have any comments after assessing the group of predefined factors?

Please provide any general thoughts on the factors listed above or any suggestions, incl. regarding potentially missing important locked factors!

Success factors in developing multi-actor project proposals

Are there any factors related to the development of multi-actor project proposals that you find important but that have not been mentioned in this questionnaire? If yes, please name these factors.

Are there any other general comments you would like to make after filling out this survey?

Success factors in developing multi-actor project proposals

Finally, we would appreciate if you could answer some demographic questions.

*** What is your gender?**

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- No answer

*** What is your age?**

- 18-25
- 26-35
- 36-45
- 46-55
- 56-65
- 66-75
- 76-85
- 86+

*** Is English your native language?**

- Yes
- No

Success factors in developing multi-actor project proposals

We thank you for your time.

To learn more about the project, please visit the project's website (<https://premiere-multiactor.eu/>).

www.premiere-multiactor.eu

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Funded by
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